

Demand-Side Innovation Policy to Achieve Sustainability Missions: The role of voluntary standards in green public procurement by municipalities

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Summary

1. Green public procurement is a demand-side innovation policy instrument that can be conceptualized as a mission-oriented innovation policy, offering a mission-oriented approach to further sustainable development progress.
2. Using a case study approach focusing on the Municipality of Amsterdam and analyzing 95 Sustainable Urban Development projects, supplemented by stakeholders interviews, we sketch 5 policy recommendations for the effective use of voluntary standards in Green Public Procurement.
3. The recommendations are (1) Standardize sustainability missions across districts; (2) Strengthen the role of standards in public tenders; (3) Boost stakeholder engagement in procurement processes; (4) Gradually uptake standards into legal frameworks; (5) Support research on standards implementation in tenders and private-sector collaboration.

1. Green public procurement is a form of mission-oriented innovation policy

Mission-oriented approaches are emerging as popular solutions for governments **to tackle contemporary sustainability challenges**, as seen in the Horizon Europe R&D program of the European Commission [1, 2] and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals [3]. The Council of the European Union emphasizes “the crucial role that public

procurement can play in the proper implementation” of the Sustainable Development Goals and the “**incorporation of these goals to serve the public interest**” [4]. Public contracting authorities can use Green Public Procurement (GPP), as a purchasing instrument which reduces environmental impacts across product or service life cycles [5], to achieve such missions. As a **demand-side innovation policy**, the GPP can be conceptualized as a type of mission-oriented innovation policy [6], thereby offering a mission-oriented

approach to further sustainable development progress.

2. Voluntary standards are critical to the practice of green public procurement

Voluntary standards and eco-labels are also demand-side innovation policy instruments to be used in public calls for tenders within GPP [5]. Voluntary standards (often referred to simply as “standards”) are **documents that specify what is required beyond regulation (if any exists)** [7]. They are created through the development of “technical specifications based on consensus amongst the interested parties” [8]. Various types of standards may be used in public procurement provided that they are “clear and ambitious” [9], based on “scientific information **using a procedure in which stakeholders, such as government bodies, consumers, manufacturers, distributors and environmental organizations can participate**” [10].

How voluntary standards are used

Voluntary standards can serve as technical specifications or award criteria in tenders. Common approaches include **mandating adherence** to specific standards in technical requirements and **awarding points** for meeting or exceeding sustainability benchmarks like the [Nearly Zero-Emission Building \(NZEB\)](#) standard. Standards can also be used for **sustainability clauses in contracts** to manage long-term performance. Additionally, procurement processes can apply **increasingly strict** sustainability criteria at various selection stages, ensuring alignment with the contracting authority's sustainability missions. This creates **competition between potential suppliers,**

rewarding those with the most sustainable products, services, or works.

3. There is a lack of knowledge on how to use standards to achieve sustainable urban development goals

Despite this potential, there exists a lack of understanding of how to theoretically situate and practically execute GPP and voluntary standards within missions-oriented innovation systems. To address this research gap, we investigated **how voluntary standards can help formulate and achieve missions for sustainable urban development** at the municipal level, followed by **what role GPP can play in this process.**

To do so, we established a theoretical synthesis of GPP and missions-oriented innovation systems. Next, using a **case study approach focusing on the municipality of Amsterdam**, we conducted an empirical investigation of **95 sustainable urban development projects**, of which 55 were public tender projects (in which the municipality is the landowner), and 40 were no-public tender projects (in which a private entity is the landowner), supplemented by **stakeholder interviews.**

Using this data, we 1) **conceptualized six sustainability ambitions** as missions and examined each for their formulation in terms of targets and associated standards, and 2) **mapped the various actors engaged** in the process of implementing these missions through sustainable urban development projects, defining their positions and interrelations within the missions-oriented innovation systems at the municipal level (Figure 1).

4. Findings

Incorporating voluntary standards in public tenders can enable municipalities to effectively leverage mission-oriented GPP to achieve sustainability goals. This approach would stimulate innovation and support the development and market penetration of sustainable products and services, particularly for urban development. It is recommended that policy actions at various levels are taken in support of this.

Our findings underpin the following conclusions and reflections relevant to policymakers.

Sustainability Missions identified for the Municipality of Amsterdam

Amsterdam pursues the challenge-based societal mission to *build a city that will last for generations and which is developed sustainably* – in other words, the **mission to transition to sustainable urban development**. The overarching mission is translated into five missions as **ambitions or goals to guide practical implementation**. Various standards are used as indicators to assess sustainability performance in sustainable urban development projects. These are presented below, per mission:

- **Sustainable Energy and a Natural Gas-Free City:** Indicators that track energy performance (EPC, BENG/NZEB standards), types of heat supply (district heating, solar, aquathermal), cooling systems, and insulation measures.
- **Cleaner Air through Emission-Free Mobility:** Metrics focus on the availability of car charging stations, modal split for

parking, shared mobility options, and sustainable construction logistics.

- **Climate Adaptation:** Indicators include rainwater storage solutions, heat mitigation measures (green roofs, facades), cool public spaces, drought-resistant infrastructure, and water safety solutions.
- **Greening Urban Spaces and Nature-Inclusive Building:** Metrics assess green area coverage, types of greenery, green standards achievement, management plans, and nature-inclusive features like green roofs and nest boxes.
- **Circular Construction and Waste/Raw Materials:** Indicators evaluate material use (types, recycled content), environmental performance scores (MPG), building adaptability, demountability, and waste management systems.

Policy implication 1: Standardize (the incorporation of) Sustainability Missions Across Districts

We found that progress toward missions is often requested across all districts of a municipality, for the city as a whole, such as by its alderman for urban planning and sustainability. For Amsterdam, the Urban Advisor is responsible for coordinating/advising on sustainable urban development projects across five geographical districts. They **connect sustainability policy at the municipality with concrete projects, translate policy into practice, and give feedback to policymakers** (Figure 2). However, this is challenging because of differences in organizing document sources, leaving it difficult to understand what is happening, with **policies leaving room for interpretation that results in high variability between districts**.

To reduce variation between sustainability ambitions between districts, **policies should be concretized and similarly approached in all documents**. Due to the strong influence that individual project members can currently have on project sustainability, **standardizing processes are expected to create more clarity for project developers and facilitate interest** in voluntarily increasing sustainability performance of non-tender projects particularly. Procedurally, this entails formal consideration of standards within the **PLABERUM process** (Figure 3), which aims to create clarity, diligence, and manageability of sustainable urban development projects across four phases.

Policy implication 2: Improve the Use of Voluntary Standards in Tender Projects

For the cases examined in this paper, and likely for many other municipalities globally, the processes for incorporating sustainability missions – as well as the sustainability missions themselves – are new. The use of voluntary standards in GPP is similarly novel. However, **there is a growing awareness and understanding of the mechanism**, where its practical implementation can feed into theoretical assessment and vice versa. Figure 4 provides a suggestion of a theoretical framework to situate different types of standards for GPP according to innovation maturity. **Providing clearer methods to incorporate voluntary standards into tender projects** is recommended to increase competition for sustainability among suppliers, particularly in the construction sector. This would indirectly enhance environmental performance.

Studies on the implementation of GPP to support missions can lead to a greater scientific understanding of the interaction

between sustainability missions and other themes. This is necessary to **explore the potential trade-offs and unintended consequences of incorporating these missions** – including via voluntary standards – into GPP. At the EU level, project calls under Horizon Europe are underway for cities to undertake progress toward sustainability missions, including via joint pre-commercial procurement and innovation procurement.

Policy implication 3: Facilitate Stakeholder Engagement in Procurement Processes

Public contracting authorities are encouraged to **adopt process-oriented procurement instruments that facilitate stakeholder engagement**, such as user needs assessments and market consultation techniques. These methods are **crucial for inclusive and effective procurement planning** and can be supported practically and via funding provided by European projects, such as [eafip](#).

Importantly, work undertaken within the Horizon Europe DemoTrans project is **identifying success factors for how to structure which market engagement activities for sustainability and innovation outcomes**, including which actors to involve. These findings will be presented in a subsequent policy brief, as well as in academic publications, a best practice guidance document, and a short video for public contracting authorities.

Policy implication 4: Examine Voluntary Standards as Catalysts for Regulatory Evolution

Tender procedures are possible when land is publicly owned, enabling the use of voluntary

standards. However, for sustainable urban development projects where the **municipality is not the landowner, private project developers must only adhere to regulatory requirements**. If these are perceived as the bare minimum in terms of sustainability performance, additional agreements between parties can lead to the incorporation of higher standards. Whether or not this occurs depends on many aspects, such as individuals employed for the project and whether an area is appointed as a pilot area. Therefore, there is no systematic integration of voluntary standards into non-tender projects.

The **gradual integration of voluntary standards into legal frameworks** is recommended to promote higher sustainability aspirations in both public tender and non-tender projects. For instance, aligning municipal policies with national environmental visions, like the [Omgevingswet](#) in the Netherlands, may **strengthen sustainability requirements and empower municipalities** to influence national regulations.

Policy implication 5: Promote Further Research

Future research should also focus on a more detailed investigation into **the formulation and specification of voluntary standards within tendering documents**, as well as **engagement with and influence of GPP projects on the private sector within MIS**. An example is to ascertain whether firms engaging in tender or non-tender projects for sustainable urban development are incorporating voluntary standards and increasing sustainability.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Figure 1. The structural components that are part of the mission-oriented innovation system having the mission to reach the sustainability ambitions of sustainable urban development. The stakeholders in green are the stakeholders that are interviewed.

Figure 2. The role of the Urban Advisor during each program component of SUD projects. Overall, they are responsible for connecting sustainability policy at the municipality with concrete projects, translating policy into practice, and giving feedback to policymakers on what is not working.

Figure 3: The PLABERUM process at the Municipality of Amsterdam.

Figure 4: Theoretical framework, as a characteristics space for innovation with standards and standardization.

Further information:

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